

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

AUTHENTICATION OF AYURVEDIC MEDICINE TRIKATU CHURNA USING NEAR INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY - A NOVEL APPROACH

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 30/11/2017

Available online

06/12/2017

Keywords

Ayurvedic,

Siddha,

Trikatu Churna,

Piper Nigrum,

Piper Longum,

Zingiber Officinale,

Chemometric,

PCA.

ABSTRACT

During the recent past, several Ayurvedic medicines have been prepared and investigated with respect to physio-chemical standardization, pharmacological effects, safety, efficacy, cultivation of medicinal plants and manufacturing practices. The objectives of this study is suggesting a novel method for the authentication of Ayurvedic and Siddha medicines to ensure the identity, quality, purity and detection of adulterants non-destructively using the spectroscopic techniques. The Ayurvedic sample *Trikatu Churna*, *TC*, taken for analysis, is a polyhedral formulation of finely powered dried fruits of *Piper nigrum*, *pn*, *Piper longum*, *pl*, and *rhizome of Zingiber officinale*, *zn*, at equal proportions. The customised TC was prepared by mixing at the equal proportion of the pure and dried raw material component powders (reference sample). The NIR spectral characteristics of customised samples were compared with the market samples (test samples) by developing a suitable Chemometric model. Accordingly, a method is proposed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) technique to bring out strong patterns from their reference TC spectra to validate test samples by identifying its identity, quality and purity non-destructively.

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Please cite this article in press as **Mudiganti Ram Krishna Rao et al.** Authentication of Ayurvedic Medicine Trikatu Churna Using Near Infrared Spectroscopy - A Novel Approach. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(11).

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INTRODUCTION

Trikatu Churna (TC) is one of the classical Ayurvedic formulation which is prescribed for Agnimandya (digestive impairment), Gala roga (throat diseased), Svasa (Asthma), Kushtha (Skin diseases), Pinasa (Sinusitis), Kasa (Cough) and Slipada (Filariasis). High Performance Thin layer Chromatography of Thrikatu churnam was reported by Sunita *et al*, 2011 in which piperine was found to an important constituent [1].

The purity aspect of ayurvedic medicines is under question due to adulterants and unscientific methods of preparations. It is high time to find out a simple, non destructive, quick and reliable method of testing the purity of these medicines. Chauhan *et al*, 2016 have studied the physicochemical parameters of the ingredients of Trikatu churnam market samples, such as loss on drying (LOD), ash value, acid insoluble ash, water soluble extract, methanol soluble extract and pH values and these parameters were found to be within normal ranges as compared with Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) standards [2]. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) system is another method to check the variation in the drug ingredients batch to batch. Mahato *et al*, 2016 have reported the standardization techniques for Trikatu churna [3].

The present study is a novel approach, in which Trikatu churnam (TC) is exposed to Near Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) to record specific spectral patterns which could be used as a tool to authenticate the medicine. A workable model for medicine authentication is suggested, which could be extended to authenticate other medicines also. Trikatu churnam consists of three ingredients, namely, black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), long pepper (*Piper longum*) and dried ginger (*Zingiber officinale*). A brief account of the medicinal aspects of the three ingredients in mentioned hereunder:

Black Pepper: *Piper Nigrum* (pn): A common house hold spice, pepper contains phytochemicals such as, piperine, alkamides, piptigrine, wisanine, dipiperamide D and dipiperamide E and the piperine content is 5-10%. Piperine belongs to the family of Alkaloids and its derivatives. The molecular formula for the piperine is $C_{17}H_{19}NO_3$ and weight is 285.343 g/mol.

Long Pepper: *Piper Longum* (pl): The main phtoconstituents of *Piper nigrum* are piperine, rutin, beta-caryophyllene, piperyline, piperoleines, piperamine, sabinene, chavicin. The piperine percentage in the long piper is 3%. The chemical structure of the piperine is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Chemical structure of the piperine.

Ginger: *Zingiber officinale* (zn): The scientific name of the ginger is Zingiber officinale and its main components are 6-gingerol, 6-shogaol and 6-paradol. This ingredient in TC used as medicine for treating nausea, dysentery, heartburn, flatulence, loss of appetite, infections, cough and bronchitis. The molecular weight of gingerol is 294.38 g/mol and the chemical formula is $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Chemical structure of the Gingerol.

Fig.3. (1) Black Pepper, *Piper nigrum* (2) Long Pepper, *Piper longum* (3) Dry Ginger, *Zingiber officinale* & (4) Trikatu Churna (Mixture of all the three ingredients).

Figure 3 shows the various ingredients for the present study.

METHODS

The three ingredients of Thrikatu churnam, TC, namely, *Piper longum*, *Piper nigrum* and *Zingiber officinale* were procured from standard Ayurvedic vendors. They were cleaned, washed with distilled water, soaked with a clean cloth and allowed to dry. The dry materials were separately ground to fine powders and sieved mechanically to have common particle sizes. The reference TC sample was prepared with the following raw materials ingredient at equal proportion and all the ingredients.

Fine powders of individual ingredients of *pl*, *pn* and *zn* and the compound of *pl* & *pn*, *pn* & *zn*, *pl* & *zn* and *pl*, *pn* & *zn* were prepared for analysis. NIR spectral signatures were collected individually for the compound samples as well the market samples using FOSS system. XDS Optiprobe analyser from FOSS NIR system was used under reflectance mode to get NIR spectra in the range of 400-2500 nm at the resolution of 0.5nm.

Near Infrared Spectrometer

The principle of NIR reflectance spectroscopy is that of light wavelength between 1100 to 2500nm, reflected off from the sample of solid, liquid and semisolids. This method can provide simultaneous rapid and non-destructive measurement of the major components in many organic substances [4, 5]. The main focus of spectroscopic technique is to assess of an organic chemical structure containing O-H, C-H, N-H and S-H bonds through the absorption of energy in the NIR region of the spectrum due to the broad overtones and combinational bands of fundamental vibrations transitions [6].

Spectral Analysis

Spectroscopy combined with chemometric methods has the potential to be a powerful tool for the assessment of the chemical composition of any given organic substance. Initially, NIR spectral signatures were collected for the three ingredients of *pl*, *pn* and *zn* (10 spectra of each ingredient) of the reference TC between the wavelength regions from 400nm to 2500nm. The spectral peaks shows the molecular interaction of C-H, O-H, N-H & CONH₂ bonds occurred around 1446nm, 1450nm, 1460nm, 1930nm & 1940nm, which contributed for *pl*, *pn* and *zn* respectively. Accordingly, the wavelength bands clipped further from 1400nm to 1613nm and 1894nm to 2006nm for analysis. Total the size of the data 30 X 4200 was reduced to 30 X 650 and was subject to classification by an unsupervised technique using Principal Component Analysis. Before doing PCA model the data was pre-processed using baseline correction and Standard Normal Variate (SNV) transformation for removal of multiplicative interference of scatter and particle size. The referred wavelength regions of TC showed significant similarity with respect to the three ingredients *pn*, *pl* and *zn*, respectively. The NIR signature of the reference TC is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Reference spectra for Trikatu ingredients.

PCA analysis was done for five test samples, of which one of the test samples was prepared by mixing of 1gm of *pl*, *pn* & *zn* ingredients (Customized Sample, CS) and four other samples were purchased from the market namely MS1, MS2, MS3 and MS4. NIR spectra of all the test samples were clipped in the referred wavelength region from 1400nm to 1613nm and 1894nm to 2006nm for PCA analysis. In total 50X650 market samples have been validated with the PCA model. The score plots for both the reference model as well the test samples are shown in the Fig. 5 and Fig.6.

Fig.5.Score plot of the reference Trikatu ingredients.

Fig.6.Score plot of the reference Trikatu ingredients with market samples.

It is understood from the above PCA score plot that the market sample MS2 is totally different when compared with other market samples and reference samples.

RESULTS

From the PCA model of TC ingredients and market samples, the plot infers the similarity among the samples. In continuation of present study, another PCA model has been presented for how well the ingredients were formulated to qualify the TC which may be accepted or not. Again a set of NIR spectra were analysed for the TC by collecting the spectra for the customised sample i. e 1gm of ingredients mixture (*pl*, *pn* & *zn*), only *pl* & *pn*, *pn* & *zn* and *pl* & *zn* mixed samples without the third ingredients. The same PCA model used to validate the chosen sample by locating its space from the cluster centre of the TC ingredients were shown respectively in Fig.7.

Fig.7. Customized sample, *pl*, *pn* & *zn* score plot spacing within the ingredients cluster.

If the sample mixture contains pure *pl* & *pn* component, then the predicated score plot moves towards the line connected the two cluster PL & PN, similarly for the *pn* & *zn* and *zn* & *pl*. The validated score plots were shown in Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig.10.

Fig.8. Customized sample, *pn* & *pl* score plot spacing within the ingredients cluster.

Fig.9. Customized sample *pl*& *zn* score plot spacing within the ingredients cluster.

Fig.10. Customized sample, *pn* & *zn* score plot spacing within the ingredients cluster.

DISCUSSION

The application of NIR spectroscopy creates a novel tool for the authentication of an Ayurvedic drug having more than one chemical component by analysing the sample's ingredient using PCA technique. There are NIR models and hand held tools to detect various food products like fruits, vegetables etc. in the market. But this seems to be the first attempt to use NIR for authentication of Ayurvedic drugs. The present PCA model was developed to study the characteristic of the TC and was compared with market samples to validate them. The spectral patterns obtained for Trikatu churnam and its individual components, were used to create a PCA score model using cluster techniques. It was observed that PCA scores of customized sample and its ingredients were lying in triangle and there orientation seemed reasonable as compared to their proportions. When the PCA of market samples MS1, MS2, MS3 and MS 4 were compared to this standard triangle, it was observed that market sample MS 2 was not coming into the triangle of the standard. Further, the model has been optimised using cluster techniques to find the specific spectral compositions of any market sample of TC, whose PCA score lies within the area of a triangle whose vertices are the principal centres of the three ingredient clusters namely *Piper nigrum* (pn), *Piper longum* (pl) and *Zinigiber officinalis* (zn). The PCA score of any test sample, which lies out of the triangle area, would mean that there could be some adulteration or the preparation could have uneven proportions, which could be further authenticated before use as medicine.

CONCLUSION

From the above study it is concluded the proposed model could be tested for other such drugs for easy, quick, non-destructive authentication. Such model is also being probed for some other medicinal formulations and in future this method could be of great use in the authentication of herbal medicines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank to the Director, CSIR-CEERI, Pilani and Scientist In-Charge, CSIR- CEERI Centre, Chennai, former Vice-chancellor of Bharath University, for their support to publish the paper.

COMPETING INTERESTS

This is to inform that no conflict of interest exist among the author.

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